

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF BIOMASS-ACTIVATED CARBONS FOR THE ADSORPTION OF PFAS IN ENVIRONMENTAL WATER

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Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are aliphatic substances with high fluorine content, increased chemical and thermal stability and high hydrophobic and lipophobic nature. These compounds are used in different manufacturing processes of products used in different fields as surface tension reducers and stain, grease and dirt repellents [1].

PFAS persist in the environment and bioaccumulate in air, water, and soil. The large use of PFAS is linked to the growing industry, generating significant contamination of effluents, surface waters, soils, groundwater, and oceans. PFAS has been found in drinking water, wastewater, surface water and even rainwater. Bioaccumulation in humans increases the risk of developing cancer, lipo-functional, liver and immune disorders, and also birth defects [2]. One of the methods for the efficient removal of PFAS from water resources is the adsorption and retention of these substances with solid porous matrices, such as biochar. These separation processes consist of passing a contaminated aqueous matrix through the biochar which contains large surface areas, microporous volume and specific functional groups. These processes are efficient and economically acceptable, therefore, the production of activated carbons for potential use in wastewater, groundwater and drinking water matrices is considered a viable solution to prevent potential damage caused by PFAS [3]. The present work exposes the development of different types of activated carbon derived from residual biomass of maize cob waste, produced through pyrolysis using physical activation with nitrogen and CO₂ and chemical activation in alkaline and acid medium. In addition, the characterization of this activated carbon was performed, considering the surface area, porosity, adsorption and regeneration capacities, to take advantage of the best characteristics for its implementation in the adsorption processes of PFAS in aqueous matrices. This work evaluates the capacity of these biomaterials to remove PFAS from aqueous solutions.

References

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